

PREFACE

The United Nations World Tourism Organization has 192 members across the globe. The member countries are guided to work towards sustainable tourism development. Tourism plays an important role in improving the living standards of the local people because tourism brings benefits in the form of infrastructure development, employment, tourism education. At present, large numbers of organizations and governments invest much money in the tourism industry. Globally, tourism has a major share in national income and employment of many countries either developing or developed. The growth in tourism industry will lead to a need for human capital with competitive skills at all levels. The trained, efficient with required level of education to cater the real time problems are needed to serve that present with futuristic skills.

Travel and tourism Industry is a young industry and job-hopping (less than two years at a position) is key characteristic among the Millennials because it can speed up career advancement and more salaries. It implies that there are multiple generations at the workplace and Millennials are not getting work culture in industry. The growth of the gig economy because of continuum transformation in technology has led to skilling, upskilling and reskilling of professionals. It can be inferred that new kinds of employment skills are needed and there is a need for lifelong learning among all the stakeholders of the tourism industry. The human capital needs for tourism industry in 2020 are not same as of 2030 will be. There will be emergence of new types of tourism, products, services, professions, skills, knowledge and personality attributes.

The importance of tourism industry in India is growing. The Indian Tourism industry is assigned the role of champion to make India a bigger economy. India has a myriad of opportunities to attract inbound tourists through diversifying the tourism products, services and competent human resource. Even many of the Indian States have proposed to increase the share of international tourism arrival, employment generation, and share of tourism earnings in State gross domestic product. The States have plans to achieve sustainable development goals through tourism development.

Chapter one: It was discussed here about the benefits of tourism, Indian tourism and its different aspects, genesis of tourism education in global and Indian perspective. The dimensions of tourism education development and life cycle of tourism education are different across the globe. The nature of tourism education varies from non-unified discipline to a tool for sustainable development or education for economic development. Tourism education has a wider role in the development of society if industry-academia are integrated. Tourism education in India is contributing towards knowledge creation along with different agencies but at a nascent stage. The multiple regulatory authorities and non standardisation of courses are big issues in the country.

Chapter two i.e. literature review tried to know about the gaps found with regards to human resources produced by academicians and demanded in industry. It provides an overview about the global scenario of tourism education and different curriculum and courses studied across the globe. Besides that tourism education and planning, human resource and tourism industry, tourism education and tourism planning, tourism education and professionalism, tourism education and sustainability, problems and future of tourism education in addition the skills and curriculum studied in different countries are discussed.

The *third chapter* explains the research methodology used in this particular research. The role and significance of the tourism industry in India is discussed in *chapter four*. The chapter connects tourism development with regards to achieving bigger national economic growth, national tourism policies, State tourism policies, tourism and employment, flagship programs of government to develop tourism infrastructure to achieve more employment share and tourism product development. There are hurdles like lacuna in policy formulation and implementation, lack of tourism professionals in public tourism organisations and decade long national tourism policies during the highly dynamic and competitive tourism world.

As tourism education is an integral and paramount component to decide the future of the tourism industry across the globe. *Chapter five* deals with the perception of tourism academicians and tourism industry professionals with regards to institutional information, years of teaching as academician and tourism professionals, programs offered by institutes and services offered by travel companies, typology of

business. In addition the opinion of respondents are analysed with regards to relevance of tourism education in the country, sustainable development, rating subject specific knowledge required in industry. The perception of respondents with regards to incorporation of Indian Tourism Services, most desired curriculum development network by academicians and professionals, and opinions of both about the change required to make tourism education close to industry need and entrepreneurship skill development among the tourism graduates.

Chapter six talks about the conclusion of the study and recommendations to improve existing tourism education in the country

This study will establish a new benchmark for curriculum development, academicians' new role, use of technology in academics, competitiveness, role of tourism graduates in national tourism planning, and integration of tourism policies along with human resource development to industry needs. It will help in creation of a pool of applied tourism knowledge through a common platform which can be used to fulfill the desired needs of the tourism industry as well as sustainable tourism development.

(Rajinder Kumar)

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CONTENTS

Chapter No.	Title	Page No.
I	INTRODUCTION	1-54
	1.1 Benefits of Tourism	
	1.2 Indian Tourism at a Glance	
	1.3 Genesis of Tourism Education	
	1.4 Nature of Tourism Education	
	1.5 Education and Tourism Education	
	1.6 Why Tourism Education?	
	1.7 Tourism Education in India	
	1.8 Indian Competitiveness at Global Platform.	
	1.9 Academia-Industry Networking in Promoting Tourism Education, Knowledge Creation-Sharing	
	1.10 Different Agencies Revamping Skills in Indian Tourism Industry	
	1.11 Lacuna in Indian Tourism Education	
	1.12 Tourism Education- For whom?	
	1.13 Threat to Tourism	
	1.14 Relevance of this Research	
II	LITERATURE REVIEW	55-108
	2.1 Tourism Education Globally: An Overview	
	2.2 Tourism Education in India	
	2.3 Tourism, Tourism Education and Employment	
	2.4 Human Resource in Tourism Industry	
	2.5 Tourism Education and Tourism Planning	
	2.6 Tourism Education and Professionalism	
	2.7 Tourism Education and Sustainability	
	2.8 Problems in Tourism Education	
	2.9 Future of Tourism Education	
	2.10 Tourism education curriculum and skills.	
	2.11 Research Gap	
III	RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	109-116
	3.1 Statement of Problem	

	3.2	Need of the Study	
	3.3	Scope of Study	
	3.4	Objectives of Study	
	3.5	Research Questions	
	3.6	Design and Framework	
	3.7	Data Sources	
	3.8	Questionnaire Design	
	3.9	Methodology	
	3.10	Delimitations of the Study	
	3.11	Limitation of the study	
IV		ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF TOURISM INDUSTRY IN INDIA	117-143
	4.1	A Glance at Indian Tourism Industry	
	4.2	Indian Context of Understanding Tourism	
	4.3	Tourism Planning in India	
	4.4	Tourism a Giant Source to Minimize Unemployment	
	4.5	Contribution of Tourism in India	
	4.6	Conclusion	
V		DATA INTERPRETATION AND ANALYSIS	145-248
	5.1	Institutional Information	
	5.2	Specialisation Offered	
	5.3	Program Information	
	5.4	Students' Profile and Employees' Profile	
	5.5	Crosstab Analysis of Opinions of Academicians Across Dropout Rate, Origin and Schooling Background; Dropout Rate and Educational Background of students	
	5.6	Opinion about Course Curriculum Development for Tourism Programs	
	5.7	Opinion on Tourism Education	
	5.8	Crosstab analysis of Satisfaction with Tourism Education Syllabus	
	5.9	Crosstab Analysis with Regards to Status of Tourism Education in India	
	5.10	Analysis of Specialisation, Rating of Tourism professionals and ITS	

- 5.11 Preference for ‘Subject Specific Knowledge’
Among Top, Middle and Low Levels of Management
- 5.12 Crosstab Analysis of Skills Enhanced and Skills Found
- 5.13 Crosstab Analysis with Regards to Desired level of
Improvement in Tourism Education Content
- 5.14 Crosstab Analysis of Academic Designation,
Management Levels and Relevance of Tourism Education

VI CONCLUSION AND RECCOMENDATION

6.1 Conclusion

6.2 Recommendations

LIST OF TABLES

Table No.	Title	Page No.
1.1	Current Status of Tourism	
1.2	Research and development under ICSSR (Tourism)	
1.3	UGC approved new colleges for B. Voc. program in tourism (2015)	
1.4	UGC approved community colleges for tourism education	
1.5	Tourism Education in State Universities	
1.6	Tourism Education in Central Universities	
1.7	Brief of travel and tourism competitive index toward India	
1.8	Various skill India programs (tourism)	
1.9	Tourism Education Programs of Ministry of Tourism	
2.1	Curriculum content	
2.2	Skills requirement in tourism industry	
4.1	World and Indian tourism verses Covid-19 impact on tourism	
4.2	Direct contribution to employment	
4.3	Total Contribution to Employment	
4.4	Direct contribution to Indian GDP	
4.5	Total contribution to GDP	
4.6	Investment (Capital Investment)	
4.7	Indian Government individual expenditure	
4.8	Domestic Tourism Spending	
4.9	Outbound Tourism Expenditure	
4.10	Visitor Exports (foreign spending)	
4.11	Business Tourism Spending	
4.12	Leisure Tourism Spending	
4.13	Internal Travel and Tourism Consumption	
5.1	Department affiliation (academicians)	

5.2	Typology/operation	
5.3	Teaching/service experience	
5.4	Infrastructure availability	
5.5	Specialization offered by institutions	
5.6	Educational background of employees	
5.7	Origin of the employees	
5.8	Dropout rate and origin/schooling background	
5.9	Educational Background of students	
5.10	Designing of Course curriculum	
5.11	Most desired approach by academicians	
5.12	Most desired approach by industry professionals	
5.13	Specific subject knowledge	
5.14	Ranking of tourism specified subject knowledge	
5.15	Opinion about skill level	
5.16	Rating of basic skills	
5.17	Opinion on areas of improvement	
5.18	Ranking as per most desired improvement	
5.19	Rating of Tourism Education by Academicians	
5.20	Rating of Tourism Education by industry professionals	
5.21	Respondents and Tourism Education	
5.22	Relevance of tourism education	
5.23	Rating of opinion regarding relevance of tourism education	
5.24	Indian Tourism Service	
5.25	Satisfaction and years of teaching	
5.26	Satisfaction and ITS	
5.27	Satisfaction and status of tourism education	
5.28	Tourism education and International Peace	
5.29	Tourism education and National Image Building	
5.30	Tourism education and Sustainable Development	
5.31	Tourism education and Economic Development	
5.32	Tourism Education and Environment Conservation	
5.33	Tourism education and product development	
5.34	Years of teaching and status of tourism education	

5.36	specialization and professionals' rating	
5.37	Specialisation and ITS	
5.38	Tourism professionals and ITS	
5.39	Level of management and of airlines and cargo management	
5.40	Level of management and Travel agent and tour operation	
5.41	Level of management and Tourism law	
5.42	Level of management and Tourism Software/application	
5.43	Level of management and Accommodation industry	
5.44	Level of management and Event Management	
5.45	Level of management and Outdoor activities knowledge	
5.46	Level of management and foreign language knowledge	
5.47	Level of management and On the Job Training practice	
5.48	Level of management and Destination Management	
5.49	Level of management and Tourism Research	
5.50	Level of management and Tourism policy	
5.51	Level of management and Management Information System	
5.52	Academic designation and confidence level incorporated	
5.53	Academic designation and foreign language	
5.54	Academic designations and communication	
5.55	Academic designations and travel software skills	
5.56	Academic designations and Outdoor Skills	
5.57	Academic designations and Research Skills	
5.58	Academic designations and Presentation Skills	
5.59	Academic designations and Digital Skills	
5.60	Academic designations and Sales Skills	
5.61	Academic designations and Marketing Skills	
5.62	Academic designations and Tourism Industry Ethics Skills	
5.63	Academic designations and Travel Ethics Skills	
5.64	Management Level and Confidence level	
5.65	Management Level and Foreign Language Skills	
5.66	Management Level and Communication Skills	
5.67	Management Level and Travel Software	

5.68	Management Level and Outdoor Skills	
5.69	Management Level and Research Skills	
5.70	Management level and Presentation Skills	
5.71	Management Level and Digital Skills	
5.72	Management Level and Sales Skills	
5.73	Management level and Marketing Skills	
5.74	Management Level and Tourism Industry Ethics Skills	
5.75	Tourism professionals and Travel Ethics Skills	
5.76	Academics and Syllabus Update	
5.77	Academics and Industry-Interaction	
5.78	Academics and Job Training	
5.79	Academics and Research	
5.80	Academics and Foreign Language	
5.81	Academics and Travel Software Training	
5.82	Academics and Digital Skills	
5.83	Academics and Library Resources	
5.84	Academics and Academia-Industry Training	
5.85	Academics and Student Exchange Programs	
5.86	Management and Frequent Syllabus Update	
5.87	Management and Industry-Interaction	
5.88	Management and Job Training	
5.89	Management and Research	
5.90	Management and Foreign Language	
5.91	Management and Tourism Software	
5.92	Management and Digital Skills	
5.93	Management and Library Resources	
5.94	Management and Academia-Industry Network	
5.95	Management and Student Exchange Program	
5.96	Academics and International Peace	
5.97	Academics and NIB	
5.98	Academics and Sustainable Development	
5.99	Academics and Economic Development	
5.100	Academician and Environment Conservation	
5.101	Tourism professionals and International Peace	

5.102	Tourism professionals and National Image Building	
5.103	Tourism professionals and Sustainable Development	
5.104	Tourism professionals and Economic Development	
5.105	Tourism professionals and Environment Conservation	

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure No.	Title	Page No.
2.1	Scheme of Literature Review	
2.2	The TEP-TEI Conceptual Framework	
2.3	The local context for curriculum	
2.4	Psychographic positions of destinations	
2.5	New age classroom	
2.6	The Philosophic Practitioner	
3.1	Organization of Research	

LIST OF GRAPHS

Graph No.	Title	Page No.
5.1	Department affiliation	
5.2	Specialized services offered a tourism professional	
5.3	Point of resemblance	
5.4	Satisfaction/year of teaching	

LIST OF CHARTS

Chart No.	Title	Page No.
5.1	Percentage of respondents among tourism academicians.	
5.2	The percentage of distribution among respondents from tourism industry.	
5.3	Any specialisation (Academicians)?	
5.4	Any specialisation (Tourism Professionals)?	
5.5	Educational Background	
5.6	Schooling of students	
5.7	Origin of student	

5.8	Skills rated by tourism professionals and tourism academicians	
5.9	Academicians and Satisfaction with syllabus	
5.10	Rating of tourism professionals	

LIST OF IMAGES

Image No.	Title	Page No.
4.1	Tourism	
4.2	Advantage of tourism in India	
5.1	Specific departments	
5.1.1	Name of specialized services	
5.2	Nature of tourism courses	
5.3	General course components that are included in the tourism programs	
5.4	Tourism course component in tourism programs	
5.5	Must require skills?	
5.6	Participation in tourism education by tourism professionals	

ABBREVIATIONS USED

ACTI	Association of Caribbean Tertiary Institution
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AICTE	All India Council for Technical Education
ARC	Australian Research Council
ASEAN	Association of Southeast Asian Nations
CAUTHE	Council of Australian Universities Tourism and Hospitality Education
CBSE	Central Board of School Education
CNTA	China National Tourism Administration
CTS	Centre for Tourism Studies
EU	European Union
HR	Human Resource
ICE-THE	International Centre of Excellence in Tourism and Hospitality Education
ICI	Indian Culinary Institute
ICSSR	Indian Council for Social Science Research
IHM	Institute of Hotel Management
IIM	Indian Institute of Management
IISM	Indian Institute of Skiing and Mountaineering
IIT	Indian Institute of Technology
IITFC	Incredible India Tourist Facilitator Certificate
IITTM	Indian Institute of Tourism and Travel Management
ITS	Indian Tourism Services
MBA	Master of Business Administration
ML	Machine Learning
MTTM	Master of(in) Travel and Tourism Management

NCHMCT	National Council of Hotel Management and Catering Technology
NSDC	National Skill Development Council
PPP	Public Private Partnership
SAARC	South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation
SPARC	Scheme for Promotion of Academic and Research Collaboration
STCRC	Sustainable Tourism Cooperative Research Centre
TAFE	Tertiary and Further Education
TEFI	Tourism Education Futures Initiative
THSC	Tourism and Hospitality Skill Council
UGC	University Grant Commission
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
UNWTO	United Nations World Tourism Organisation
VET	Vocational Education and Training
BEST	Building Education for Sustainable Tourism